

The Application of Technology Acceptance Model in Evaluating Mixed Reality as a Learning Strategy on Classroom Management

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Abstract

Information and communication technologies have a significant impact on daily living. One of the impacts is the use of information and communication technologies to affect the school and college learning process. Previously, Mixed Reality (MR) in conjunction with Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) was the global problem requiring investigation. In many nations, it is acknowledged that this technology facilitates learning. Using the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) variable correlation for the evaluation process, this study intends to determine how mixed reality is utilized in the education sector. In this study, 300 students employing mixed reality technology served as responders, and 286 valid assessments of Mixed Reality procedures or methods were collected through questionnaire. Using SPSS and AMOS, the variables were examined. All variables utilized in the experiment were shown to be dependable, yet there were various hypotheses with unaffected findings in this technology. Among the findings are that the quality of the supplied information/learning material has no influence on the perceived ease of use or the amount of enjoyment felt by students. In addition, the perception of Ease of Use by students when utilizing mixed reality as a learning medium had no effect on the students' learning-related attitudes. In this scenario, it can be determined that, based on the Technology Acceptance Model variable, the usage of mixed reality as one of the supporting learning techniques, taking into account the Quality of Information and Interactivity of the learning material, is already being utilized appropriately. Suggestions for future study include the use of this application on other items, the addition of variables that can be utilized in sectors other than education, and the addition of variables other than TAM so that it may be used in a variety of contexts.

Keywords: *Mixed reality, Learning Strategy, Augmented reality, Virtual reality, Technology Acceptance Model.*

INTRODUCTION

The existence of information and communication technology development conveys a lot of influences in daily lives particularly in a school or college level. One of the technology which is popular in the social world is Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR). Therefore, there is a lot of studies which identify the strength, opportunity, challenge, and impact of the use of this technology VR and AR have a deep impact in education sphere (Choi & Totten, 2012; Di Serio et al., 2013). Beside, AR is also used for educational purposes, where AR can be considered as a crucial factor in a learning process activity (Manis & Choi, 2019; Kaur et al., 2021). Another research mentioned that in retail industry AR can increase knowledge and influence students trust towards the education (Bigne et al., 2016). In addition, the use of AR can be a supporting tool for creating situations as if students can see what they want to see in reality (Elkaseh et al., 2016). In the hotel and tourist industries, the usage of virtual reality (VR) is crucial for increasing visitors once the technology is integrated into the marketing plan (Tsai, 2015). It enables technicians, for instance, to learn new techniques in real time within the education and training industry (Abdullah & Toycan, 2017). AR technology has advanced and shown its dominance over VR technology (Assegaf, 2015). Compared to regular education classes, AR technology affords pupils options. Due of its pedagogical benefits, augmented reality in education gains popularity (Hsu et al., 2010). In light of the presence of these two technologies, the researcher sought to utilize VR as a learning innovation to enhance the quality of learning at the college level. Mixed Reality describes the confluence of these two technologies (MR). MR is a type of augmented reality that permits the placement of digitally created items in real time (Ho & Kuo, 2010).

VR can be used for simulation-based teaching in educational context. The implementation for VR can also be used in field trips, training and design. AR can potentially boost up students minds through narrative technology. The implementation for AR is prominent in augmented reality in the classroom, distance learning and marketing in education (Safar et al., 2016). The common use of these by students, their innovative and highly attractive features are characteristics that open multiple educational options (Olsson & Salo, 2011). In this research, the researchers intend to analyze any further variables that have big impact to the satisfaction of technology using of VR and AR among college students. There are some variables which can be used in analyzing student's motivations in utilizing VR and AR. The hypothesis of this research is that the more the students are motivated in learning, the better they can improve their passion in extending knowledge they learn.

During this time the use of technology mixed reality be considered as an appropriate technology for many fields, but have not seen any research on the variables that significantly affect the satisfaction of the students within the learning process using mixed reality itself if it is associated with technology acceptance variable. So, this research is considered important so that in the future the developers of the technology of mixed reality pay more attention to the variables that influence the satisfaction of the students during the learning process, and this study shows how good if mixed reality is used as one of the learning strategy.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Mixed Reality (MR)

Extending the physical world and combining real-world and virtual-world objects are conceivable in the new richer settings enabled by Augmented Reality (AR) and other recent advances in technology (Barhorst et al., 2021). The definition of augmented reality is a real-time view of the actual environment that is enriched by computer-generated virtual data, such as a digital image or video stream (Elmqaddem, 2019). Although there are several definitions of augmented reality, there are recurring themes about its characteristics, such as information quality, interaction, perceived utility, perceived ease of use, pleasure, attitude, behavioral aim, and satisfaction (Sannikov et al., 2015). In recent years, AR has grown in importance in the realm of education (Tekedere & Goke, 2016; Shiue et al., 2019). AR materials may successfully boost the academic enthusiasm of students and facilitate effective learning (Sural, 2018). Frost et al. (2020) first characterized VR without any hardware references as an experience in which "the student is successfully engaged in a responsive virtual environment." In the meanwhile, an immersive computing technology (ICT) that includes a "set of technologies that enables pupils to experience a world beyond reality in an immersive manner" gave an updated alternative definition of virtual reality that included a hardware component (Lopes et al., 2019). These definitions distinguish between a virtual reality experience, virtual reality content, and virtual reality hardware in a deliberate manner. In addition, the enhanced merging of the actual and virtual worlds generates an experience that is consistently distinct. This study demonstrates that students' attention may be captured by novel (unique) material encountered via AR technology during information processing, leading them to get absorbed in the activity (Aso et al., 2021). In augmented reality (AR), a 3D computer-generated environment is seamlessly integrated with the actual world (Tashko & Elena, 2015). VR is a new technology with a small body of evidence of varying methodological quality (Saleem et al., 2021). Additionally, VR may be a feasible instructional approach for enhancing information acquisition (Iqbal & Sidhu, 2019).

Quality of Information

Utilizing the classic technology acceptance model (TAM) to attain this objective based on ease of use, usefulness, and attitude is the starting point of this study. Yen et al. (2013) include additional particular factors connected to interactive technology, such as information quality, aesthetic quality, reaction speed, and interactive reliance on the idea of student experience (Kesim & Ozarslan, 2012). As predicted, prior research concentrated on the educational experience and included more functional criteria, such as the site's speed and content quality (Weeks et al., 2021). Consequently, the vividness of the information might heighten the sense of the quality of the information by increasing the number of sensory dimensions, which may enhance cognitive processing (Millett et al., 2012). Similar to interaction, vividness enables students to see usage and forthcoming experiences in their minds (Abd Majid et al., 2015). Items were employed to assess information quality (modified from Oh et al., 2013) and interactivity (adapted from Muk & Chung, 2015). One item was used to assess perceived usefulness (adapted from Choi & Totten, 2012); two items were used to assess perceived enjoyment (adapted from Manis & Choi, 2019); three items were used to assess perceived ease of use (adapted from Yen et al., 2013); four items were used to assess perceived behavioral intention (adapted from Kesim & Ozarslan, 2012); and five items were used to assess perceived attitude (adapted from Kesim & Ozarslan, 2012). (adapted from Weeks et al., 2021). Then there were items used to perceive satisfaction (adapted from Millet et al., 2012).

Based on several previous studies, it can be interpreted that the quality of information has considerably influenced perceived usefulness. However, the quality of information has only a slight impact on the perceived ease of use that is felt by students, and the Quality of information does not significantly affect the sense of enjoyment that mixed reality students feel. The quality of the information obtained in the process of learning become basic things considered. Then the quality of the information into the needs in the field of education, especially for learners. Quality of information has a significant and positive influence on perceived usefulness (Kashada et al., 2020). The use of MR for the learning process of the students will determine the level of perceived usefulness. It supports for the results of H1 (affects perceived usefulness). The perception of ease of use can positively and significantly affect the quality of information (Parise et al., 2016). Then the quality of the information necessary to facilitate the learning activities of students. The results of these studies produce H2 (affects perceived ease of use). The perception of enjoyment can positively and significantly affect the quality of information (Javornik, 2016). Enjoyment can also affect the quality of the information received by the students. Then H3 (affects enjoyment) was the result of the hypothesis in this study. Three hypotheses below affect the quality of information in the field of education. We hypothesized:

H1 : Quality of information affects perceived usefulness.

H2 : Quality of information affects perceived ease of use.

H3 : Quality of information affects enjoyment.

Interactivity

Although there are continuous disagreements over the idea of flow, one of the most frequently debated aspects of flow is interaction (Petit et al., 2019). It is stated that interactivity is the capability of a technology system to allow users to readily interact, control, modify, and engage with material (Yim et al., 2017). Interactivity may be seen from two complimentary perspectives: (1) the technological characteristics and (2) the students' perspectives (Van Noort et al., 2012). In addition, such a comprehensive examination of method interaction provides an understanding of the function of AR interactivity.

Lee et al. (2019) discussed the significance of technological characteristics in determining interactivity based on the technology employed. From the standpoint of a student's perception, interactivity consists of an individual's subjective sense of actual or virtual interactivity (Lee et al., 2019). Moreover, computer-generated things that connect with virtual objects in the physical world are inherently involved in the exploitation of AR technology. AR technology is probably one of the most engaging forms of technology due to the aforementioned high levels of student engagement (Pantano et al., 2017). Due to its interactivity, augmented reality (AR) involves the manipulation of both the actual and virtual worlds, and it goes beyond the screen (Rese et al., 2014). We anticipated (Hastuti et al., 2019) that such students' contact with the interactive elements may induce an absorbing state of mind, hence immersing the individual in the activity and favorably impacting the state of flow (Woon et al., 2021).

Based on these previous studies, it can be concluded that the level of Interactivity of a mixed reality has an impact on the extent of perceived usefulness, which has an impact on the perceived ease of use for students because it is considered easier for students, and the level of Interactivity in mixed reality determines the extent to which students perceive enjoyment. Basically in the process of learning required interactivity. Between the teacher and the student or students with teachers. This can be a parameters of the level of understanding on the matter said. Then the interactivity used as the hypothesis in this study. The interactivity of the AR technology will more positively influence the usefulness of flow than a traditional shopping experience (Abdullah & Toycan, 2017). Similar to the interactivity of students in the learning process, H4, i.e. interactivity affects perceived usefulness, is discussed. Interactivity positively and significantly influences the ease of use of a students from experiencing the virtual (Bigne et al., 2016). Easy experience using MR technology will help students in understanding the material. Therefore, hypothesis H5 is generated, that is, interactivity affects perceived ease of use. Interactivity positively and significantly influences the enjoyment of students' perception from experiencing the virtual (Choi & Totten, 2012). In addition, enjoyment during use also affects the interactivity provided. This results in a hypothesis H6 (affects enjoyment). So, we hypothesized:

H4 : Interactivity affects perceived usefulness.

H5 : Interactivity affects perceived ease of use.

H6 : Interactivity affects enjoyment.

Technology Acceptance Models (TAM)

To reach this objective, the current study used the technology acceptance model (TAM) based on perceived utility, perceived ease of use, enjoyment, attitude, and behavioral attention (Elkaseh et al., 2016). The suggested conceptual model outlines the properties of technology, including aesthetic quality, interaction, response speed, and information quality. In addition to the usual TAM dimensions (perceived utility, perceived ease of use, pleasure, attitude, and behavioral attention), a new dimension has been identified (Assegaf, 2015). Because TAM has been extensively investigated in a number of situations by previous academics (Bigne et al., 2016), it provides a suitable framework for research examining acceptance, usage, and subsequent behavioral outcomes in education.

Perceived Usefulness

In a particular environment, maintaining beliefs (i.e., perceived utility and perceived ease of use) is effective (Elmqaddem, 2019). Therefore, he argued that researchers should first confront their own research-specific attitudes. Relevant beliefs are those that "function as factors of" one's attitude. Frost et al. (2020) identified perceived utility as the most important belief for the adoption of technology; nevertheless, it is advisable to note that Iqbal & Sidhu (2019) added another belief variable, felt enjoyment. Consequently, each concept is handled briefly.

Previously, perceived usefulness was defined as "the extent to which a person feels that utilizing a certain system will improve his or her job performance." Several studies considering perceived usefulness employ the definition of Hastuti et al. (2019) excluding "job." In light of the definitions of usefulness and perceived usefulness, it is evident that the original construction of perceived usefulness lacks quality information and interactivity, including: (1) perceived usefulness; (2) enjoyment; (3) perceived ease of use; (4) behavioral intention; and (5) attitude as a technology acclimation model to

satisfaction. This study defines perceived usefulness as the degree to which an individual feels adopting a given system would be desirable and beneficial. Multiple usage contexts have verified the association between perceived ease of use and perceived utility; however, this relationship has not been evaluated in the context of VR gear (Hsu et al., 2010). Currently, with a large amount of secret VR material, the perceived utility of VR may be significantly lower than gaming, the use of TAM in relevant prior settings.

It can be demonstrated from these investigations that the amount of perceived utility in implementing mixed reality produces distinct behavioral intention patterns. In addition, the perceived usefulness of mixed reality also affects the attitude that the students will show, and because of that, perceived usefulness will affect the level of enjoyment felt by mixed reality students. High perception of usefulness will increase the effect on students of behavioral intention (Kashada et al., 2020). Study of the use of the object of the consumer. However, perceived usefulness also affect behavioral intention. Therefore, hypothesis H7 is specified, that is, perceived usefulness affect behavioral intention. Perceived usefulness positively and significantly influences consumers' attitude (Kesim & Ozarslan, 2012). Attitude is also needed for the learning activities of students in understanding the material. This results in a hypothesis H8, that is, perceived usefulness affects attitude. Perceived enjoyment has a significant and positive influence on consumer (Manis & Choi, 2019). Enjoyment in the use of MR is not just for the consumer. However, students also need to understand the material. Because the pleasure will affect the level of understanding of the material in the can. Then hypothesis H9 is determined, namely, perceived usefulness affects enjoyment. So, from these several bases, our hypothesized are stated as follows:

H7 : Perceived usefulness affects behavioral intention.

H8 : Perceived usefulness affects attitude.

H9 : Perceived usefulness affects enjoyment.

Perceived Ease of Use

Pantano et al. (2017) define perceived ease of use as "the extent to which a person feels that utilizing a given technology would be effortless." Several later research, including Olsson et al. (2013), have utilized the original definition given by Muk & Chung (2015); nonetheless, the original definition proposed by Muk & Chung (2015) is more prominent. Analyses are being conducted on perceived usefulness, the second primary indicator of confidence in the first TAM model.

Some of these studies show that the level of perceived ease of use in the application of mixed reality can lead to different behavioral intentions according to the level of ease of use. In addition, perceived ease of use in mixed reality also affects the attitude of its students, although not very significant. So, perceived ease of use will also affect the level of enjoyment felt by mixed reality students, generally the higher the level of perceived ease of use, the higher the level of enjoyment felt by student. The ease in the use of learning media, namely technology. This becomes the main priority of the student in understanding the material. Then teachers need to provide a simulation that the use of technology is easy. The results of the research revealed two attitudinal-behavioral relationships: (1) attitude to purchase VR hardware and intention to purchase VR hardware, and (2) the attitude to use VR hardware and intention to use VR hardware (Oh et al., 2013). Perceived ease of use has a significant and positive relationship with consumers' attitude towards (Petit et al., 2019). From the results of research between behavioral intention and attitude have a relationship in order to facilitate the use of MR. Perceived ease of use is positively and significantly associated with students perceived enjoyment (Safar et al., 2016). In addition it is a pleasure to be a supporting factor in the use of the MR by the students. Then it is determined the two hypotheses, namely H10 (i.e. Perceived ease of use affects behavioral intention), H11 (i.e. Perceived ease of use affects attitude), and H12 (Perceived ease of use affects enjoyment). So, from these several bases, we hypothesize:

H10 : Perceived ease of use affects behavioral intention.

H11 : Perceived ease of use affects attitude.

H12 : Perceived ease of use affects enjoyment.

Enjoyment

Petit et al. (2019) define perceived pleasure as "the extent to which the action of utilizing technology is judged to be pleasurable in and of itself, independent of any anticipated performance outcomes." Academics have determined that enjoyment is a significant motivator for the adoption of new technologies. Saleem et al. (2021) expand the original TAM by include subjective satisfaction as an additional intrinsic motivating driver of technological acceptance. It serves as an additional belief variable in this model. Next, we shall investigate attitudes and their formation. Based on these prior research, it is prudent to add pleasure perception.

After studying several previous studies, it can be seen that the level of enjoyment can affect many things, including influencing behavioral intention, in which when something feels good, it creates good behavioral intention as well. Besides that, the feeling of enjoyment when using mixed reality also affects the attitude raised by its students. And the last thing is that the more students enjoy using mixed reality, the higher the level of satisfaction felt by these students. It will certainly be the parameters of the level of understanding of students. Then the factor of enjoyment in the learning process is greatly determine the outcome of learning, in the field of education. When comparing the path coefficients of the relationship

between beliefs and attitudes towards using and purchasing VR hardware. Perceived enjoyment emerges as the most powerful predictor relative to the other belief variables (Sannikov et al., 2015). Pleasure gives effect to the behavioral intention and attitude because these factors can help students' understanding. So both hypothesis, H13 (affects behavioral intention) and H14 (affects attitude) are generated. Enjoyment will have a more positive effect on satisfaction with the experience when the use of AR technology is part of the experience (Tashko & Elena, 2015). The result of the parameter determines the hypothesis H15 (affects satisfaction). Because of the enjoyment in the use of MR based on the satisfaction of material provided. Thus, the following hypotheses are formulated:

H13 : Enjoyment affects behavioral intention.

H14 : Enjoyment affects attitude.

H15 : Enjoyment affects satisfaction.

Attitude

According to the conventional conception, an attitude is a stable and consistent condition of preparedness to act (Shiue et al., 2019). The old approach assumed a continually updated predisposition, either as a result of current mental processes or relevant situational elements, functioning as a concise evaluative summary of an attitudinal object (i.e., behavior, individuals, places, goods, topics, and ideas) (Sural, 2018). When anything is provided with an attitudinal object and there is a concurrent requirement to determine the object of attitude, a stored object that comes to mind is that evaluation instinctively regulates thought and aids in directing behavior. Others propose a more practical definition of an attitude as an appraisal of an attitudinal object as having a positive or negative valence, as being liked or disliked, or as being favorable or unfavorable. In addition, the perceived ease of use of VR during the preprototype stage may have a role in some aspects. A higher role is played since the hardware's capability does not maximize the application's efficiency or effectiveness. Against this background, the outcomes of perceived usability and actual usability must be evaluated. Perceived utility of purchasing attitude and VR hardware attitude. Several prior studies have demonstrated that the attitude of mixed reality users influences their behavioral intention; if the user's attitude is positive, their behavioral intention will also be positive. Moreover, attitude influences satisfaction. If users of mixed reality have an incorrect mindset, it might result in unhappiness with the technology. Teachers must have a positive learning attitude. So that pupils have the attitude that is reflective of the material's explanation. Consequently, attitude influences behavior intention and contentment. Attitude toward the adoption of the virtual try-on system effects the later behavioral intention to utilize the system in a favorable and substantial manner (Van Noort et al., 2012). Then attitude can affect the behavioral intention of students. So that the students can have good attitude. It is influenced by behavioral intention. Hypothesis H16 (Attitude affects behavioral intention) is determined in this study. Customer's attitude is proven to have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction (Woon et al., 2021). Also, attitude affects satisfaction to the students. This affects understanding of the material by the students. Then the specified hypothesis H17 (Attitude affect satisfaction). Based on this account, the designed hypothesis is as follows:

H16 : Attitude affects behavioral intention.

H17 : Attitude affects satisfaction.

Behavioral Intention

Theoretically, behavioral intention is a person's deliberately formed plan to conduct or engage in a specific activity. Examining the link between attitude and behavior by reviewing and analyzing previous research. The key hypothesis of Woon et al (2021) 's study is that the strength of an attitude-behavior association depends on the degree of correspondence between the attitudinal and behavioral entities [41]. This study evaluated VR hardware based on the quality of information and interactivity, including: (1) perceived utility; (2) enjoyment; (3) perceived ease of use; (4) behavioral intention; and (5) attitude as a model of technological adaptation to satisfaction. Thus, we analysed the things included in this model as an extension of the antecedent variables initial TAM. Based on some of these research results, it can be assumed that Behavioral intention has an impact on satisfaction, where the higher the level of Behavioral intention, the higher the satisfaction obtained. Behavioral intention is related to the previous factor, namely ethics. But in this study, it aims to determine the behavioral intention which influences satisfaction, especially in using technology while learning. Based on the research results the positive significant relationship between behavioral intention to use and actual usage Yen et al. (2013). Behavioral intention affects satisfaction to the students. So the determination of the hypothesis H18 (Behavioral intention affects satisfaction) based on the previous research. Therefore, that the following hypothesis is obtained:

H18 : Behavioral intention affects satisfaction.

Satisfaction

The examination of satisfaction within the management system has a long history. Numerous studies have been undertaken within the realm of end-user computing to gather overall assessments where end users have evaluated pupils of an information system (e.g., contentment) and the elements that influence satisfaction. End User Computing Satisfaction (EUCS) is a method for measuring the level of student satisfaction with an application system by comparing students' expectations with the actual performance of an information system. End User Computing - Definition Students' overall rating of an information system based on their experience using the system is its satisfaction. This EUCS assessment methodology was designed (Yim et al., 2017). This evaluation methodology stresses end-user satisfaction with technological features by evaluating the system's content, correctness, format, speed, and usability. This model's dependability has been evaluated by other researchers, and the results indicate that there are no major changes between the translated versions of this instrument (Yen et al., 2013).

Information and communication technology is very helpful in everyday life, one of which is during the pandemic which disrupted various sectors of life, one of which is education. Current education is done through online learning. However, when problems occur in the field, online learning has several complaints from the academic community. The complaint mainly deals with that the material presented was monotonous and boring. This is due to the lack of a group discussion forum (unlike face-to-face learning). So from this problem utilization via AR is deemed appropriate. AR that makes users feel like they are in real life. Of course this will make learning more fun and less boring. Besides that, the advantages possessed by AR are a form of visualization of the various objects needed. However, this needs to be reviewed, because not all AR can be used such as software specifications that must be adequate, stable internet access and others.

In several previous studies the influence of the TAM variable to the use of mixed reality, measuring mixed reality user satisfaction have been discussed, and there were also researchers who explained the effect of the satisfaction variable on the decision to use mixed reality. In this study, a comprehensive model development was carried out by measuring the influence of TAM on mixed reality user satisfaction based on several variables that support satisfaction and the decision to use mixed reality in the learning process, so that the use of the reality mixer is taken into consideration as an alternative strategy in making learning innovations.

METHOD

Figure 1 is the framework for the research model used in this study, where the framework is structured based on hypotheses that have been formed previously through various theories and research that have been carried out by previous researchers.

Figure 1: Research Models

This research was conducted using a questionnaire containing 37 questions from 8 variables that have been compiled as shown in Table 1 research questionnaire. By using a Likert scale ranging from 1-5, where a scale of 1 indicates a non-conformity and a scale of 5 indicates a very suitable sign. This research was conducted by using purposive sampling technique, where the sampling was carried out based on a specific objective that required special respondents using mixed reality technology. In this study, the number of respondents who participated was 300 people who were students at the college where the researcher worked. After a valid test was carried out, it was shown that the respondent data who met the criteria were only 286 respondents, and this number was used in the data processing and testing process. The next statistic in order to process the model that has been designed.

Table 1. Research Questionnaire

Quality of Information.
a. I feel that the material presented in mixed reality suits my expectations.
b. I got a complete display of lecture material from this mixed reality technology.
c. I feel that this material is suitable and relevant to be presented using mixed reality technology.
d. Mixed reality helps me to understand the essence of this course material.
e. I feel that mixed reality technology is quite clear in conveying material compared to other technologies.

Interactivity
a. I have free control when using mixed reality in the learning process.
b. I can determine the course material that I will learn using mixed reality.
c. I can control learning pace using this technology.
d. I feel that mixed reality technology is quite effective and efficient to be used as a medium of learning.
Perceived Usefulness
a. I feel more productive in learning using mixed reality.
b. Mixed reality helps me understand the material more effectively.
c. Mixed reality offers more opportunities to understand material more quickly at any time.
d. Mixed reality gives me more insight in understanding learning technology.
e. The learning process becomes more efficient by using mixed reality.
Enjoyment
a. Mixed Reality makes me enjoy learning the materials delivered in a clear voice, and I can repeat learning if needed.
b. Mixed Reality helps me learning materials in 3D reality.
c. I feel happy using mixed reality as a learning medium
d. Mixed Realities facilitates me learning the course materials.
e. I feel impressed using mixed reality in the learning process.
Perceived Ease of Use
a. I feel the use of mixed reality provides ease in understanding learning materials.
b. Mixed Realities helps me understand the materials easily.
c. I feel that mixed reality is able to describe the course material clearly.
d. I feel that mixed reality makes course materials more informative and flexible when applied in the learning process.
e. Personally, I find that I can learn the materials easily using mixed reality.
Behavioral Intention
a. Most likely I will use mixed reality more often as a medium to understand lecture material.
b. I am used to using mixed reality in understanding lecture material.
c. In the future, I will use mixed reality to understand other things.
d. In my opinion, mixed reality will be very much needed in the future in many fields.
Attitude
a. In my opinion, mixed reality is very good to be used as a learning medium.
b. Mixed reality makes me more excited about the learning process.
c. For me, mixed reality has a positive impact as a learning medium.
d. For me, mixed reality provides many advantages when used as a learning medium.
e. Mixed reality brings its own pleasure when understanding learning materials.
Satisfaction
a. I feel satisfied using mixed reality to understand course material
b. Mixed Reality can fulfill my needs in illustrating course material descriptions.
c. I feel that mixed reality makes the learning process easier to understand.
d. I feel that mixed reality helps me achieve the required understanding in lecture materials.

Source: data proceed

This study was conducted using a variety of statistical tests to evaluate the questionnaire's effectiveness as a survey tool. The first statistical test to be conducted is a validity test to evaluate the questionnaire's validity. It examines if all inquiries are pertinent to a certain objective. If r-value is more than r-table, the questionnaire is viewed as legitimate; nevertheless, if r-value is less than r-table, the questionnaire is interpreted as invalid. In addition, a test of dependability was conducted to determine the consistency of the results while assessing the same symptoms. After the first two tests have been conducted, a normality test is conducted to determine whether the data are normally distributed. SPSS19 is utilized for testing. Following the completion of the three tests, the confirmatory factor analysis and goodness of fit are conducted. In this step, the model is processed using AMOS 22 software and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). This analysis is undertaken to demonstrate the link between the design model's variables, so that it can be determined which variables mutually influence one another.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity, Reliability, and Normality Test Results

As mentioned earlier, tests of validity, reliability, and normality were carried out on 286 data. The validity test results show that the range of each r-value is valued from the lowest 0.382 to the highest 0.746. The researcher interpreted that each question was valid because the test results showed a value higher than the r-table, namely ≥ 0.153 . Furthermore, the reliability test on each variable showed that all values for each Alpha Cronbach had a higher value than Alpha Cronbach's ≥ 0.8 . This means that the variables used are all reliable. In addition, the results of the normality test based on the scatterplot and KMO - Bartlett's Test show that the data is normal because each plot is spread in one line to the top right of the graph. The KMO test result value is 0.954 with a Bartlett value of 0.000 indicating a high-test sensitivity. The determination standard based on Hair et al. in his book entitled "Multivariate Data Analysis".

Confirmatory Factor Analysis and Goodness of Fit Results

The building blocks that connect each indicator with the main variables are used to construct constructs. Researchers used six variables in this study, each construct is made by these variables. The indicators for each variable in testing using AMOS 22 are estimated to have a value of ≥ 0.70 to be accepted. Conversely, if the value does not reach the estimated value, it must be omitted.

SEM Model

The following Figure 2 shows a model that has been analyzed using SEM, which is indicated by a solid line arrow or a dotted line, which shows whether the variable affects significantly or not.

Figure 2. Result SEM Analysis

----- : Not Significant value
 ____ : Significant value

The estimated value reveals the impact between factors based on the SEM analysis findings. The effect between variables is stronger the stronger the association between variables. In the SEM model, parameter estimation requirements exist when the build reliability is 0.70. The analysis of the test results is depicted in Table 2, which demonstrates that the value of each indicator and variable satisfies the requirements since each construct of reliability is less than 0.70.

Table 2. Variable Estimated

Variable/Construct	Construct Reliability	Decision
Quality of Information	0.838	Reliable
Interactivity	0.755	Reliable
Perceived Usefulness	0.857	Reliable
Perceived Ease of Use	0.841	Reliable
Enjoyment	0.823	Reliable
Behavioral Intention	0.856	Reliable
Attitude	0.872	Reliable
Satisfaction	0.861	Reliable

Source: data proceed

Thus, the goodness of fit index test can be done because the complete model has met the reliability and validity requirements. Table 3 below illustrates the results of the goodness of fit index that have been analyzed.

Table 3. Goodness of Fit Table

Goodness of Fit Index	Cut of Value	Value	Model Decision
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CMIN/DF	< 2.0	0.0015	Good
RMSEA	< 0.8	0.740	Good
NFI	> 0.9	0.901	Good
CFI	> 0.9	0.804	Moderate
GFI	> 0.9	0.903	Good

Source: data proceed

Based on the results of the goodness of fit index analysis in Table 2, it can be observed that the Fit Model with CMIN/DF value is 0.0015, which means that the Model is good. Meanwhile the RMSEA (root mean square error of approximation) value is indicated by the number 0.740 which means the criteria are good. CFI (Comparative Fit Index) of 0.804 means that it is in the category ≥ 0.90 [83]. GFI (goodness of fit index) is 0.903, in this model the GFI value is close to 1, and so it is classified as a good model. In addition, from the results of this analysis, the t-value and P. value are obtained, where if the t-value is above 1.96, it indicates a good model, and P value is below 0.05 indicates that the correlation of the variables in the model is significant. The determination of the cut of value of a table based on Hair et al. In his book entitled "Multivariate Data Analysis" [83]. Table 4 below illustrates the hypothesis decisions for the model that has been designed.

Table 4. Result of Proposed Hypothesis Analysis

	Hypothesis	t-value ≥ 1.96	P (<0.05)	Decision
H1	Quality of information affects perceived usefulness	2.210	.027	Significantly Affected
H2	Quality of information affects perceived ease of use	1.744	.081	Not Affected
H3	Quality of information affects enjoyment	1.210	.226	Not Affected
H4	Interactivity affects perceived usefulness	2.800	.005	Significantly Affected
H5	Interactivity affects perceived ease of use	2.486	.013	Significantly Affected
H6	Interactivity affects enjoyment	2.115	.012	Significantly Affected
H7	Perceived usefulness affects behavioral intention	3.226	.001	Significantly Affected
H8	Perceived usefulness affects attitude	2.965	.003	Significantly Affected
H9	Perceived usefulness affects enjoyment	2.817	.006	Significantly Affected
H10	Perceived ease of use affects behavioral intention	2.554	.011	Significantly Affected
H11	Perceived ease of use affects attitude	3.747	.301	Not Affected
H12	Perceived ease of use affects enjoyment	2.236	.022	Significantly Affected
H13	Enjoyment affects behavioral intention	3.539	***	Significantly Affected
H14	Enjoyment affects attitude	2.936	***	Significantly Affected
H15	Enjoyment affects satisfaction	9.257	***	Significantly Affected
H16	Attitude affects behavioral intention	1.973	***	Significantly Affected
H17	Attitude affects satisfaction	3.809	***	Significantly Affected
H18	Behavioral intention affects satisfaction	8.281	***	Significantly Affected

Source: data proceed

Based on the results of the hypothesis analysis in Table 4 that has been carried out, there are 3 hypotheses that have no effect on other variables, including H2 where in fact the quality of information does not have a significant effect on perceived ease of use. This result is supported by Cabero-Almenara et al. That the quality of information does not affect the perceived ease of use. However it is also back on the situation and the media used. It is also based on the result of the determination and calculation of the t-value and P [83, 84]. In addition, at H3 the level of enjoyment also on the survey results did not show that it was influenced by the quality of information. This result is also supported by Cabero-Almenara et al. That the quality of information does not affect the enjoyment (Tsai, 2015). It is also back on the situation and the media used. It is also based on the result of the determination and calculation of the t-value and P (Takedere & Goke, 2016). And on H11 it showed that perceived ease of use had no significant effect on attitude. But the results of this hypothesis is also in line with the Pantano et al. and Sweet et al. That perceived ease of use had no significant affect on attitude. It is also based on the result of the determination and calculation of the t-value and P. These three unaffected hypotheses are supported by several previous studies that have been described in the literature review.

CONCLUSION

Based on research that has been done, it can be concluded that of the 18 hypotheses designed, there are 3 unsuitable hypotheses (no significant effect) in other variables, including H2 which explains that information quality does not affect the perception of ease of use. This shows that the ease of students in using mixed reality is not influenced by the quality of the material presented, but only influenced by the interactivity level owned by Mixed Reality itself. In addition, the H3 is explained that the quality of information also has no effect on the Enjoyment, where the sense of energy is not produced based on the quality of information/lecture material presented. Because, according to the results obtained, the sense of

energy depends more on how high the level of student interactivity with mixed reality technology when used in learning, in the perceived usefulness that students feel when using mixed reality, and in the perceived ease of use students who are felt by students during the learning process. The more interactive mixed reality technology design, the more beneficial technology in meeting student learning needs, and the easier Mixed Reality technology is used, the more enjoyment students feel during learning process. Furthermore, it is related to H11 where it is shown that the perceived ease of use when using mixed reality has no effect on student attitude in using mixed reality. In other words, student attitude is more influenced by perceived usefulness and a sense of enjoyment when using the mixed reality technology during the process learn.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

In conducting this research, the author states that there is no Conflict of Interest whatsoever in the process of publishing this scientific article.

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